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“A TASTE OF ONE’S CULTURE”

Each society has its own culture. As Raymond Williams (1958) said, culture is ordinary. It is in the way of life and the behavior of individuals. This lifestyle may be affected by what is made available by the economy, the behavior of individuals in a specific society, and the values and beliefs they practice. There may be more to this about culture, and this may not be the limiting definition of culture because culture is dynamic. Individuals act in accordance with their perception of what is accepted or not in society. This perception is heavily influenced by the existing traditions and belief system of the society which they are a part of. Thus, culture is part of the formula in the make-up of one’s identity and that of the country’s perceived identity.

You are what you eat, as the saying goes, and this talks so much about one’s identity and the meaning people can derive from the food on the plate. Food can differentiate societies and individuals, at the same time creating identities and cultures. On the other hand, the culture of a society affects the kind of food present on the table. As Almerico (2014) pointed out, culture is not inherited; it is learned, and so are the food we make.

The Philippines is historically rich with stories of colonization and how it redeemed its freedom. With every era in the Philippine history comes a great number of cultural influences from the colonizers. Colonization brought changes in cultures, beliefs, and traditions. The differences between communities established different types of cultures and identities amongst Filipinos. At the same time, it built a more general, saturated identity in terms of religion which founded our similarities (Shackford, 1990).

Food anywhere is a source of energy and life. Also, food is a source of identifying the culture of one country. For this reason, one would realize that what is called as Filipino culture is a mixture of all other cultures which influenced the nation. This is the same with food. Going back to history, Asian and European flavors are part of the fusion which we call as Filipino cuisine (Sim, 2018). During pre-colonization era, the process of trading introduced varying tastes as a result of Malay influence from China and Indian trade, Arabian Islamization, Spanish and American colonization, and additionally a global mixture through interaction.

The evolution of food-its preparation, taste and ingredients-is a reflection of the evolution of the identity of cultures. As Stuart Hall (1996) pointed out in his anthology about culture and identity, is it possible that this modernity which we are experiencing may result in a crisis of identity?

In the past, the back of the house served a lot of needed ingredients to complete the dish. The mixture of these ingredients is what makes one tradition different from that of the others. The choices individuals make

when eating, as embedded in them by the society where they grew from, is a cultural act. The food one eats based on the palate's preference is a cultural choice built by choices made available by economics, by society and by people who may have dictated what they should or should not eat starting from when they were little up to now. Making use of the idea of cultural identity based on the actions and decisions of the group one belongs to is still made evident by our food choices, whether these choices are the more traditional or modern dishes served to us. The past is a reflection of who we are now. Our palates, though not familiar with all tastes, somehow direct us to enjoy the experiences of reliving and enjoying the old cuisines, while savoring the new, presented with a twist.

The indigenization of the food presentation, use of ingredients and taste of the cuisines changed the landscape of the Philippine culture and saturated it to a more globalized taste, with a change in the process of preparation and use of ingredients. The evidence of this indigenization by using the available ingredients, utensils and even process is an adoption to the new era of culinary arts. The revival of the food of the past is a look-back of the culture we once had.

